

Impact of Job Satisfaction, Work Motivation, and Employee Performance at the National Land Agency in Makassar City

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Abstract:- This study examines the effect of job satisfaction and work motivation on the performance of BPN Makassar City employees. This research is included in the type of explanatory research that is non-experimental. The population in this study was 61 employees of the National Land Agency of Makassar city, while the sample size was as large as the total population, namely: 61 employees. The results of this study show that job satisfaction has a significant effect on employee performance, and work motivation has a significant effect on employee performance. Furthermore, job satisfaction and work motivation have a significant effect on the performance of employees of the National Land Agency in Makassar City.

Keywords:- Job Satisfaction; Work Motivation; Performance; Official.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human resources for an organization are the most important and most important resources among other resources. Human resources are a determining factor in how the resources owned can be optimally utilized in achieving organizational performance. Management needs to understand the factors that can affect employee performance, including job satisfaction, work motivation and employee commitment (Apridar and Marbawi Adamy, 2017). Job satisfaction plays a critical role in the retention of key talent. Firms can enhance prospects by creating a work environment that incorporates a positive atmosphere. Both supervisor support and potential for career development help optimize the impact of work atmosphere on employee job satisfaction levels (Abuhashesh, at. al. 2019).

Employees with a high level of job satisfaction certainly have high morale, so that work efficiency will also be maximized (Anwar et al, 2022). On the other hand, employees have low job satisfaction which leads to poor performance. Employees have a vested interest in work, which will greatly affect the Agency (Rahman et al, 2022). Employee performance has an impact on the maximum performance of an agency. For this reason, employee job satisfaction is considered very important, especially to support the company's performance in facing competition in the era of globalization (Wijaya, 2014).

Agencies also need to pay attention to how to maintain and manage employee motivation so that it is always high and focused on the goals of the Agency (Ismail et al, 2022). Maintaining employee motivation is very important because motivation is something that encourages individuals to act and do something (Nawawi, 2015). People will not do things optimistically if they do not have a strong motivation in themselves to do it (Sahabuddin et al, 2021). A process that describes the intensity, direction and perseverance of the individual in achieving the goal. From this definition, it can be seen that motivation becomes a very important factor that sustains a person or someone to do something or achieve a certain desired goal (Wahab, 2012).

Related to the importance of job satisfaction and motivation, in research at the National Land Agency in Makassar, as the National Land Agency, namely a non-ministerial government agency, it is necessary to pay attention to job satisfaction and employee work motivation. The following is data on the number of employees at the National Land Agency of Makassar City, the data can be seen in table 1, namely:

Table 1. Number of employees of the Makassar City National Land Agency in 2022.

No.	Unit/Province	Total
1.	Makassar City Land Office	1
2.	Administrative Subdivisions	8
3.	Surveying and Mapping Section	22
4.	Rights Determination and Registration Section	16
5.	Structuring and Empowerment Sections	3
6.	Land Acquisition and Development Section	5
7.	Control and Handling Section Dispute	6
		61

Source: Makassar City National Land Agency, 2022

The table above shows the number of employees of the National Land Agency in the city of Makassar in 2022 amounting to 61 employees which are divided into several parts, namely: the Makassar City Land Office with 1 employee, the Administrative Subdivision with 8 employees, the Survey and Mapping Section with 22 employees, the Determination and Financing Section with 16 employees, the Structuring and

Empowerment Section with 3 employees, The Land Acquisition and Development Section has 5 employees, and the Dispute Control and Handling Section has 6 employees.

Based on preliminary observations, it was found that in achieving the target at the National Land Agency in Makassar, the realization was not always achieved. This has led to reports of people complaining about the slow and untimely performance of BPN Makassar city employees in completing their work such as the completion of land management (Syamsuddin et al, 2022). The phenomenon of work motivation that occurs at the National Land Agency of Makassar City is explained, namely to meet needs by determining the direction of behavior (Dewi et al, 2022). By providing physical encouragement such as rewarding employees who have good behavior and have a hard work level.

Meanwhile, the form of job satisfaction given to the National Land Agency of Makassar city is to provide a beautiful and beautiful environment (Dyaja et al, 2018). Employees so that employees do not easily feel bored and saturated in the work environment and provide the appropriate type of work in their respective fields and carry out social activities that can help improve good relations between fellow colleagues (Karim et al, 2021). This can encourage employees to be able to improve their performance and be able to work optimally.

II. METHODS

This research was conducted at the National Land Agency (BPN) of Makassar City. Population is a combination of all elements in the form of events, things or people that have characteristics that are the center of attention of a researcher because they are seen as research (Ferdinand, 2006). In this study, employees of the National Land Agency showed that in 2022 there were 61 employees, this number is the population in the study. The sample is a part of the whole and the characteristics possessed by a population, the sample in this study was taken from the total population of 61 employees, because the number is not too much and can be calculated using SPSS.

The classical assumption test is a test carried out to provide certainty that the equations used have accuracy in inconsistent estimates (Nurjanna et al, 2022). This study has several classical assumption tests, including: (1) Normality test, (2) Multicholnearity test, and (3) Heterochedasticity test.

Multiple linear regression is a regression model that lists more than one independent variable. This analysis is used to determine the direction and how much influence independent variables have on dependent variables. The multiple linear regression model can be explained by the following equation:

$$Y = \beta + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + e$$

Information:

Y = Employee Performance

X₁ = Job Satisfaction

X₂ = Work Motivation

β = Slope or Estimate coefficient.

β₁ = Regression coefficient X₁

β₂ = Regression coefficient X₂

e = error

III. RESULT

The respondents in this study were employees who worked at the Office of the National Land Agency (BPN) makassar city. The following is an overview of respondents' identities consisting of gender and level of education.

Table 1. Respondent's Gender

No.	Gender	Number	Percentage
1.	Male	34	55.74%
2.	Women	27	44.26%
Total		61	100%

Source: Research results, 2022.

Table 2. Respondent's Education Level

No.	Level Education	Number	Percentage
1.	S1	56	91,8%
2.	S2	4	6,56%
3.	S3	1	1,64%
4.	Other	0	0%
Total		61	100%

Source: Research results, 2022

The variables used in this study were job satisfaction, work motivation and employee performance. These variables will be tested with descriptive statistics.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistical Analysis

Variabel	N	Minimu m	Maximu m	Mean	Std. Deviati on
Job Satisfacti on	61	31.00	44.00	37.67 21	3.63649
Work Motivatio n	61	29.00	45.00	36.44 26	4.28379
Employee Performa nce	61	31.00	45.00	37.83 61	3.86514
Valid N (listwise)	61				

Source: Research results, 2022

The validity test (validity test) is a tool used to measure the validity of a questionnaire. The validity test is carried out by testing the correlation between the item scores and the total score of each variable, using pearson corelation. The question item is said to be valid if the significant level is below 0.05.

Reliability test is a tool for measuring a questionnaire which is an indicator of a variable or construct. This reliability test was carried out to test the consistency of answers from respondents through the questions given, using the Cronbach Alpha statistical method with a significance used of more than (>) 0.6. The results of reliability testing are as follows.

Table 4. Reliability Test Results

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha	Keterangan
Job Satisfaction	0,805	Reliabel
Work Motivation	0,881	Reliabel
Employee Performance	0,866	Reliabel

Source: Research results, 2022

The variables of job satisfaction, work motivation and employee performance have cronbach's alpha values greater than 0.6. This shows that the question items in this study are reliable. So that each question item used will be able to obtain consistent data and if the question is asked again, it will get a relatively similar answer to the previous answer. The data normality test is used to find out whether in a regression model, the resulting error has a normal distribution or not. In this study to test the normality of the data, the test results of which can be seen in the figure below:

Fig 1. Normality Test Results

Based on figure 1, it can be seen that the dots spread around the diagonal line, as well as the direction of their spread follows the direction of the diagonal line. This suggests that the regression model is feasible because it meets the assumption of normality.

The multicollinearity test aims to see whether or not there is a high correlation between independent variables in a multiple linear regression model. If there is a high correlation among its independent variables, then the relationship between an independent variable and its dependent variable becomes disrupted. To test multicollinearity, it can be seen from the tolerance value and the VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) value. If the VIF value is not more than 10 and the tolerance value is not less than 0.1 then the model can be said to be free from multicollinearity (Sunjoyo, et al., 2013). The results of the multicollinearity test can be seen in the following table:

Table 5. Multicollinearity Test Results

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		
Job Satisfaction	.602	1.662
Work Motivation	.602	1.662

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

Source: Research results, 2022

Based on table 5, it can be seen that the variables of job satisfaction and work motivation have tolerance values above 0.1 and VIFs smaller than 10. It is argued that in the regression equation model there are no symptoms of multicollinearity so the data can be used in this study. The heteroskedasticity test aims to see if there is a variance dissimilarity in the residual from one observation to another. Detection of heteroskedasticity can be done by scatterplot method where the spread of the resulting points is formed randomly, does not form a certain pattern and the direction of spread is above or below the number 0 on the Y axis. The results of the heteroskedasticity test can be seen in the figure below:

Fig 2. Heteroskedasticity Test Results

Source: Research results, 2022.

The results of the hypothesis test show that the variable job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The higher the employee's job satisfaction, the more employee performance increases. A person's satisfaction and dissatisfaction with work is a subjective state, which is the result of a conclusion based on a comparison of what is actually received from his work compared to what he expects, wants and thinks as appropriate and entitled to him (Sahabuddin et al, 2022). Job satisfaction is influenced by the fulfillment of needs (need fulfilment), the difference between the expected results and their acquisition from the workplace, the value of the work to the individual, the balance of rewards and genetic factors.

Mentally challenging work, employees tend to prefer jobs that give them the opportunity to use their skills and abilities (Suryawan & Salsabilah, 2022). It offers a variety of tasks, freedom, and feedback on how well they work. Less challenging jobs create boredom, but overly challenging creates frustration and feelings of failure. In moderate challenging conditions, most employees will experience

pleasure and satisfaction (Romansyah, 2016). Favorable working conditions, employees care about the work environment both for personal comfort and to facilitate the work of good tasks.

(Most employees prefer to work close to home, with relatively modern facilities and adequate equipment. Supportive colleagues, people earn more than just tangible money or achievements and their work (Rahim et al, 2022). Therefore having friendly and supportive colleagues provides increased job satisfaction.

The results of the hypothesis test show that the variable work motivation has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The higher the employee's work motivation, the more it will make their performance increase (Afrisal & Sahabuddin, 2022). A motivated person whose desire to meet his daily needs encourages the employee to work better. The view of psychologists that humans need an involvement in a role both physical and psychological is in order to meet their basic needs (Karim et al, 2022). Maslow divides the levels of needs on a model known as the hierarchy of needs. Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory appears that each individual in general has needs that have been arranged in stages from the most basic, namely physiological needs to the highest needs, namely self-actualization, so that each individual will try to satisfy his needs hierarchically by trying to meet the needs of physiology first then increase to the fulfillment of the needs of security, the need for affection, the need for self-esteem, to the needs of self-actualization.

IV. DISCUSSION

The results of the hypothesis test show that the variables of job satisfaction and work motivation simultaneously (together) have a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The higher the job satisfaction and work motivation of employees, the more their performance will increase. If employees are paid a salary commensurate with the energy that has been used, it will make employees feel satisfied at work (Mujiatun, 2017). So that employees will be motivated to work. Motivation plays an important role in the human being, because there will be no one to meet all our needs, and will not get what we want except by trying to achieve it ourselves.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the data that has been collected and hypothesis testing with multiple linear regression analysis has been carried out, the conclusions of this study are as follows:

- Job satisfaction has a positive and significant influence on employee performance. The higher the employee's job satisfaction, the more it will make their performance increase.
- Work motivation has a positive and significant influence on employee performance. The higher the employee's work motivation, the more it will make their performance increase.

- Job satisfaction and work motivation simultaneously have a positive and significant influence on employee performance. The higher the job satisfaction and work motivation of employees, the more their performance will increase.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Afrisal, M., & Sahabuddin, R. (2022). Strategi Ombudsman Republik Indonesia Perwakilan Sulawesi Selatan dalam Meningkatkan Kepatuhan Pemerintah Kota Makassar terhadap Standar Pelayanan Publik. *Jurnal Mirai Management*, 7(2), 172-190.
- [2]. Anwar, A., Sahabuddin, R., Rahman, F. A., & Ruma, Z. (2022). Pengaruh Komunikasi Pimpinan terhadap Semangat Kerja melalui Kepercayaan Karyawan pada Telkom Divisi Regional VII Makassar. *YUME: Journal of Management*, 5(2), 25-38.
- [3]. Dewi, R., Azis, M., Rauf, A., Sahabuddin, R., & Karim, A. (2022). Empowering Communities on the Feasibility of Local Chicken Livestock Business in South Sulawesi Province, Indonesia. *Specialis Ugdymas*, 1(43), 11034-11045.
- [4]. Djaya, A. A., Imran, C., & Sahabuddin, R. (2018). The influence of entrepreneurship learning and individual commitment toward achievement motivation and its impact on the interest of business establishment for vocational high school students in Makassar, Indonesia. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 20(8), 10-14.
- [5]. Ferdinand. (2006). *Metode Penelitian Manajemen*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro, 223.
- [6]. Ismail, M., Sahabuddin, R., Idrus, M. I., & Karim, A. (2022). Faktor Mempengaruhi Keputusan Pembelian pada Online Marketplace pada Mahasiswa Universitas Hasanuddin. *SEIKO: Journal of Management & Business*, 5(1), 49-59.
- [7]. Karim, A., Musa, C. I., Sahabuddin, R., & Azis, M. (2021). The Increase of Rural Economy at Baraka Sub-District through Village Funds. *The Winners*, 22(1), 89-95. <https://doi.org/10.21512/tw.v22i1.7013>
- [8]. Karim, A., Syamsuddin, I., Jumarding, A., & Amrullah, A. (2022). The Effect of Gender Independence and Leadership Style on Audit Quality in Makassar Public Accounting Offices. *International Journal of Social Science Research and Review*, 5(7), 114-126.
- [9]. Mujiatun, S. (2017). Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja Dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Rajawali Nusindo Medan. *Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 16(2). <http://dx.doi.org/10.30596%2Fjimb.v16i2.957>
- [10]. Nawawi, M. T. (2015). Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja, Dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan/ti Dengan Komitmen Organisasional Sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi Karyawan Outsourcing PT. J Yang Ditempatkan Di Kampus II Untar Jakarta). *Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis Indonesia*, 3(1), 129-147. <https://doi.org/10.31843/jmbi.v3i1.75>

- [11]. Nurjanna, S. E., Ak, M., & Romansyah Sahabuddin, S. E. (2022). Keputusan Berwirausaha Kalangan Wanita di Kota Makassar. Nas Media Pustaka.
- [12]. Rahim, S., Wahyuni, N., Anzhari, A. M., & Karim, A. (2022). Determination Of Audit Quality: Auditor Gender Stereotype Study in South Sulawesi Province, Indonesia. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(11), 569-586.
- [13]. Rahman, F. A., Anwar, A., Sahabuddin, R., & Ruma, Z. (2022). Pengaruh Motivasi, Lingkungan Kerja dan Kompetensi terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Telkom Witel Makassar. *YUME: Journal of Management*, 5(2), 39-46.
- [14]. Romansyah Sahabuddin, R. S. (2016). Development of business values and behaviours: Takalar district, South Sulawesi (Indonesia) case study. *Actual Problems of Economics*, 2(176), 440-449.
- [15]. Sahabuddin, D. R., Idrus, D. M. I., & Abdul Karim, S. E. (2021). Pengantar Statistika. Sahabuddin, R., Rahman, F. A., Ruma, Z., & Anwar, A. (2022). Pengaruh Dimensi Marketing Mix terhadap Minat Beli Konsumen Pada PT. Alfa Retailindo (Carrefour) Pengayoman Makassar. *YUME: Journal of Management*, 5(2), 47-57.
- [16]. Suryawan, I. N., & Salsabilla, A. (2022). Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja, Disiplin Kerja Dan Motivasi Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan. *Aksara: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan Nonformal*, 8(1), 137-146. <http://dx.doi.org/10.37905/aksara.8.1.137-146.2022>
- [17]. Syamsuddin, I., Muhammad, P. N., & Karim, A. (2022). Analisis Kinerja Anggaran Belanja pada Komisi Pemilihan Umum Provinsi Sulawesi Barat Tahun 2018-2020. *YUME: Journal of Management*, 5(2), 170-177.
- [18]. Wahab, R. (2012). Pengaruh Kepuasan Kerja Dan Motivasi Kerja terhadap Kinerja Karyawan PT. Bank Mandiri . Makassar: Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Hasanuddin, 35.
- [19]. Wijaya, F. J. (2014). Pengaruh Komitmen Organisasional dan Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan Terhadap Organizational Citizenship Behavior di PT XYZ Surabaya. *AGORA* , Vol.2 No.2, 2.